

Rules of Participation for Training

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¹ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/funding-opportunities/co-creation-requests>

Introduction

This document is an additional output of the workshop *Training in the European Open Science Cloud* that was held in The Hague, The Netherlands from 26-28 February 2020. The full report of the workshop can be found in [Zenodo](#). The report contains an overall description of the workshop and results regarding Rules of Participation and practical guidance for implementation of the Rules of Participation for training service providers.

This document *Rules of Participation for training* is based on the original report and is created at the request of the EOSC Working Group Rules of Participation. This document presents a separate set of Rules of Participation for training, whereas the original report integrates the proposed training Rules in the Rules for Services and Data. The two versions differ in presentation, not in intention. In both the report and this document we have taken the draft EOSC Rules of Participation (v0.2)² as our starting point.

- The Rules of Participation concerning data are also applicable to training materials. Training materials can be both digital and analogue.
- The Rules of Participation concerning services are also applicable to training service providers. An organisation providing training is considered a service provider, more specifically, a training service provider. A service provider can provide training either solely or in conjunction with other services. Any service provider who provides training on EOSC Services, Open Science and/or the FAIR data principles is subject to these Rules of Participation. For instance, an organisation providing an IT service in EOSC may provide also training on this service.

General remarks on the draft EOSC RoP (v0.2) with regard to training

Below the quoted text from the draft EOSC Rules of Participation (v0.2) is presented in italics font.

Introduction:

*The Rules of Participation (RoP) for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) apply to all **digital resources** made accessible via EOSC, including data and services*

Comment by Training workshop: In the context of training, the proposed Rules of Participation are also applicable to non-digital resources like books and human experts.

Ground rules

G1 EOSC is open to all

Comment by Training workshop: There should be more clarification on the openness of the EOSC resources, e.g. the training catalogue or the resources in such a catalogue. There was a lot of discussion during the workshop on the feasibility of all training resources being open and free at the point of access (or rather the point of use). It was felt that the business model in relation to training could present challenges to implement.

G2 EOSC resources are registered in an EOSC recognised catalogue.

See the [workshop report](#) chapter 3 'Recommendations regarding practical guidance for training service providers' and specifically the recommendations for a federated EOSC training catalogue. The recommendations regarding the training catalogue can be summarised as: Use standards for describing training materials, ensure harvestability and discoverability, describe policies to support quality control for training materials, and comply with FAIR principles.

² <https://repository.eoscsecretariat.eu/index.php/s/QWd7tZ7xSWJsesn#pdfviewer>

RoPs for training

Note: The footnotes and references like '(see rule Op4)' that can be found in the EOSC Rules of Participation (v0.2) are not repeated in the Rules of Participation for training below.

T1. Training services and materials³ exposed through EOSC are free of charge at the point of use.

- General information about all registered EOSC training resources (metadata) is universally available through EOSC.
- Users of training materials and services in EOSC are entitled to find and access individual training materials and services free at the point of use⁴.
- Access to certain training resources and services where appropriate may require personal or organisational registration, authentication or authorisation.
- Automated and bulk downloads of training resources or the use of training resources that require a related service to be accessible, constitute a case of service consumption.
- Where usage of training services requires significant human and/or technical resources there may need to be additional means of compensation.

T2. Providers of training services and training materials adhere to principles of proper (research⁵) conduct.

- Producers of training materials agree to act in accordance with commonly agreed principles regarding the conduct of research and do not willfully misrepresent or provide false data.
- Training service providers agree to adhere to community-agreed principles and best practices regarding training provision.

T3. Terms or conditions of use are determined and published by the training service providers and the producers of training materials.

- This includes Licensing and Terms and Conditions of use and whether access requires authentication and/or authorisation.
- Providers of training materials and services define and publish their own quality targets and agree that EOSC operators may monitor and report on the level of usage of their training materials through EOSC.

T4. Providers of training materials will respect principles of FAIR data.

- Providers and producers of training materials aim to implement the FAIR principles.
- The terms of use comply with the FAIR principles and any relevant licensing, legal and ethical constraints on how data can be accessed, processed, analysed, changed and redistributed by users of training materials.
- The scope of EOSC training provision should advance the use of EOSC Services and the knowledge and implementation of Open Science and the FAIR data principles.

T5. Training Services align with EOSC service architecture

³ Training *resources* and training *materials* are synonyms in this document.

⁴ The recommended change is in alignment with note 5 of "[Solutions for a Sustainable EOSC - A tinman report from the EOSC Sustainability Working Group](#)" (December 2019): "*Free at the point of use* does not imply *Free of charge*. Free at the point of use means the end-user does not pay directly for the service when it is delivered but their consumption will be paid for by other means." That report's use of the term "service" can easily be extended to include the notion of "data" as used in the Rules of Participation (see also rule S1).

⁵ Providing a service is probably not research. Therefore this Rule is not limited to research conduct.

- Training Services comply with EOSC architectural standards where applicable, for example regarding API access, discoverability and aggregation, so that composite services and workflows can be built that integrate service use.
- Training services comply with community-accepted standards and architecture to facilitate interoperability and reuse⁶.
- Services requiring authentication or authorisation will support the use of relevant community recognised academic credentials for federated AAI.

T6. Users of training materials and training services adhere to the terms of use.

- Users agree to adhere to, and to not willfully violate, any terms of use associated with the training materials.

T7. Users of training materials and training services reference the source.

- Users of training materials agree to reference the source of the training materials, if required to do so, in every communication where they make use of, or refer to, the training materials.
- Where a persistent identifier is provided for the resource or the training services this will be quoted in the reference.
- If required to do so, users of training materials will also acknowledge the intellectual work of the original creator(s) of the training materials.
- Where the resource stipulates a standard form for this reference or acknowledgment, this form will be used by the user.
- Training Service users agree to reference the training service they use, and if required, the intellectual work of its original creator(s), in every communication where they make use of, or refer to the service⁷.
- Where the training service stipulates a standard form for this acknowledgment this form will be used by the user.

T8. Training Service providers provide users access to training on how to use their services.

- Service providers provide training on the services that they provide, e.g. on IT services, or they enable other training service providers to do so.

⁶ For example, the Sharable Content Object Reference Model (SCORM) and Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI). Discipline-independent standards around many aspects of training are still emerging, hence the importance of “community-accepted” standards.

⁷ A training service, with related training materials, may have creator(s) and/or publisher(s); users agree to reference all of them.